

A Soul Who Smiled

Aditya Bikram Mishra

A new form for others to see,

a new vigour,

a new incarnation,

yet beneath the skin,

beneath the colours,

beneath the years,

remained the same soul.

A soul with a purpose.

A solitary soul,

content to walk

where no road existed.

A soul that wandered

through meadows,

mangroves,

rivers,

hills,

oceans,

and dark nights.

Not in search of applause,

nor in search of a crowd,

but in search of answers.

And after all the journeys,

all the moults,

all the incarnations,
it remained
what it had always been:
a soul with a purpose,
a solitary soul,
yet a soul for a smile.
A smile for its own work,
a quiet self-satisfaction,
knowing it had walked
the road it believed in.

A smile for itself,
not because it was praised,
not because it was understood,
not because it was rewarded,
but because it remained true
to the purpose it carried within.

In all its moults,
it harmed no one,
nor did it stop another
from walking his own road.

The journey of moults
passed before its eyes,
each form,
each skill,
each strength acquired,
not as a burden,

but as a companion.

And through it all,

it kept smiling.

A smile for itself,

content and untroubled,

whether noticed

or unnoticed.

For the moult

was for others to see.

The soul within

remained unchanged.

And before bidding adieu,

it smiled at itself-

satisfied,

at peace,

and grateful

to have played its role.

Aditya Mishra